

**A PHILOSOPHICAL APPROACH TO THE PROBLEMS OF NEIGHBORHOOD,
PERSON, AND EDUCATION**

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Abstract. *In this article, the issue of educating young people, who are considered to be our future generation that determines the development of society, as individuals, the benefits of neighborhood and family, school cooperation, is discussed in a philosophical manner. Also, the article defines the concepts of neighborhood, family, and person. A lot of information is also given about the main psychological characteristics of the person.*

Key words: *neighborhood, family, education, person, youth, school, society, philosophical approach, psychological state, result.*

**ФИЛОСОФСКИЙ ПОДХОД К ПРОБЛЕМАМ СОСЕДСТВА, ЛИЧНОСТИ И
ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ**

Аннотация. *В данной статье в философском ключе рассматривается вопрос воспитания молодежи, которая считается нашим будущим поколением, определяющим развитие общества, как личностей, преимуществ соседства и семьи, школьного сотрудничества. Также в статье даются определения понятий соседства, семьи и личности. Также дается много информации об основных психологических характеристиках личности.*

Ключевые слова: *соседство, семья, воспитание, личность, молодежь, школа, общество, философский подход, психологическое состояние, результат.*

The rapid development of society and the increasing complexity of activities lead to the increase of invisible effects on the mind of a person. In this situation, a person's current knowledge, skills, and abilities are lacking. First of all, people feel the need for taste, insight, intelligence, manners, and emotional culture, which is formed in the family. Aesthetic, moral and other qualities of education are becoming a necessity of everyday life. Naturally, such qualities are founded and perfected through family upbringing. True, the role of social education in this cannot be denied.

From this point of view, if we rely on their unity and mutual cooperation, it is possible to achieve success in education of a well-rounded person. Family education is one of the complex problems in pedagogy. Its complexity lies in the fact that each family is a primitive group of its own, and education is based only on the characteristics of this group.

By the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5938 dated February 18, 2020 "On measures to improve the socio-spiritual environment in society, further support the neighborhood institution, and bring the system of work with family and women to a new level", the scientific and practical research center "Family" under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the republican "Mahalla Ziyasi" "Neighborhood and Family" Research Institute (hereinafter referred to as the Institute) under the Ministry of Neighborhood and Family Support of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established on the basis of the educational and methodological center.[1]

Always having peace in the family, actively organizing free time, organizing family trips to places of culture and art serve to ensure family harmony.

Mahalla is a social space of the Uzbek people formed over the centuries, where the role of education in shaping the philosophical outlook of young people in the spirit of national values is considered deep and lively. In education, combining a wide range of experiences and interactions with the real world, which contributes to the intellectual, moral and emotional development of young people, has a positive effect. In society, the community has a special role in expanding the philosophical outlook of young people through education, teaching them critical thinking in the process of education, connecting their moral judgments with a sense of national citizenship serves the future. One of the important places of education in the development of the philosophical outlook of young people in the neighborhood is the development of critical thinking skills. In this regard, the head of our state commented, "A unique system of social development is being formed in our country. In this regard, our programs such as "Prosperous village", "Prosperous neighborhood", "Youth are our future", "Five positive initiatives" play an important role in mobilizing the population to think and work in a new way.

As a result, the architectural image of hundreds of districts, cities and villages is being completely renewed.

Acquainting young people with moral values, teaching them the right knowledge, and encouraging them to think deeply about modern sciences play a decisive role in their education.

Through community discussions and reasoning on moral issues, students enrich their social views, consider the impact of their actions on others, and understand the importance of ethical behavior in personal and social situations.

This aspect of education is important in shaping individuals who are not only knowledgeable, but also possess a strong moral compass, enabling them to navigate the complexities of modern life with integrity and compassion. In today's interconnected world, educating neighborhood youth about global issues and cultural diversity is critical to developing their philosophical outlook. Education with a global perspective helps young people understand their place in the wider society and instills a sense of responsibility towards global issues.

By studying different cultures, histories, and societal structures, students become more empathetic and open-minded, qualities essential to philosophical inquiry and the promotion of a just world. Community involvement and service opportunities are inseparable from the role of education in improving the philosophical outlook of neighborhood youth. By participating in community service projects, students apply their knowledge in real-world settings that enrich their understanding of social justice, civic responsibility, and the value of contributing to the common good.

"For this purpose, vocational training centers will be established in neighborhoods. In this case, subsidies are given to training centers for each person trained in a profession, and to citizens who want to start their own business" [2].

These experiences not only reinforce the practical application of philosophical principles, but also strengthen connections between youth and their communities, fostering a sense of belonging and purpose.

Addressing the issue of educational focus on improving the philosophical thinking of neighborhood youth involves a multifaceted approach to curriculum development, teaching methodology, community participation, and addressing socio-economic issues. The goal is to create an educational environment that not only imparts knowledge, but also encourages critical thinking, ethical reasoning, and reflective thinking among young people. These efforts are very important to develop a well-rounded person who can make a positive contribution to society.

One of the main problems in education today is the lack of attention to philosophy and critical thinking in the standard curriculum. Schools often prioritize subjects that are considered important for the future, leaving philosophy out as an elective or an extracurricular activity.

This integration may include teaching philosophy through stories for young children, transitioning to formal philosophical discussions and ethical discussions for older students. Such content encourages young people to ask questions, think and form their own views on various issues, and cultivates a culture of research and reflection. Traditional teaching methods, which often rely on rote memorization and standardized tests, are ineffective for encouraging philosophical thinking.

The neighborhood has a great role in forming an educational direction and developing philosophical thinking among young people. Strengthening partnerships between neighborhood schools and community organizations can provide students with real-world contexts for philosophical exploration of environmental knowledge, moral values, social justice, and civic responsibility.

Recognizing and evaluating the participation of young people in society from different perspectives also contributes greatly to the educational environment.

The role of education in expanding the worldview of neighborhood youth is bright and deep. Education, in its broadest sense, includes not only formal schooling, but also informal learning experiences in the community. It serves as a bridge between the local environment and the vast, complex world beyond.

Enables young people to develop a deeper understanding of different cultures, societies and global issues.

Cultivating critical thinking, promoting moral reasoning, and encouraging public participation have a positive effect on the formation of the philosophical outlook of young people. Philosophical worldview developed in young people through education leads not only to acquiring knowledge, but also to the formation of individuals who are compassionate and strive to positively change the world.

One of the main conditions for proper upbringing of a child in the family is unity in education. The issue of education is complex, and it is important to carry out such a hugely responsible and honorable work in cooperation with the family, neighborhood, school and the general public.

The advantage of the neighborhood is that it is inhabited by people who have lived together for many years, know each other, tried and known each other. They are well aware of the environment in each family and the upbringing of each child, the place, status and opportunities of their parents in the neighborhood.

Creating a family, neighborhood, school cooperation plan:

➤ Conduct educational activities with every child living in the neighborhood based on the program of conducting educational activities.

➤ To create an opportunity for children to have fun and engage in interesting activities in the neighborhood.

➤ Increasing the influence of education in the neighborhood. Conducting many such activities creates ample opportunities for students to receive an all-round moral education.

A person is a separate individual, essentially a whole socio-moral universe.

He embodies the essence of man, his value as a being. The person is interpreted differently in social and humanitarian sciences from the point of view of his direction, research object and purpose. It can become a source of research in terms of biological, physiological, social, spiritual, spiritual, moral and aesthetic intelligence, as an object of thought, even philosophically and logically, in terms of the right to live and the logic of life.

The factors of personality formation are many and varied. For example, genetic (breeding), biological-natural, cultural, social life experience, relationships with fellow species, etc. The genetic aspect of a person is determined by his genetic background, physiognomy and character inherited from his ancestors, and the biophysiological aspect is determined by individual needs, such as getting energy for living, eating, engaging in sexual intercourse and leaving offspring.

A person, in essence, is a representative of certain generations based on social-historical tradition, lifestyle and experience, who are cultured, have the ability to manage their activities through consciousness, intelligence. The personality phenomenon embodies all the complexities of the human world. In order to study it comprehensively, research was conducted in different periods.

Especially in the East, it was understood through high moral and spiritual standards and was considered a high quality, priceless value. As a person, a person strives for perfection, enriches the meaning of life, and on this basis feels the need for a beautiful and prosperous human society.

A person's way of life is directly related to the life of society and he has the right to use life's benefits to the full. The concept of personality is the highest form of the human concept, the highest status. Every person is a creature with natural existence, right to life and value of life.

However, he may not be a full-fledged person all the time.

Increasing attention to the field of education and training has been adopted by our government, and in order to effectively implement the documents and administrative instructions,

it is necessary for family, community, and school cooperation to have their own pedagogical system, methods and forms. The events held should be thorough in every way, therefore, they should be pedagogical and psychological, suitable for the youth of the participants, logically deep, interesting and demonstrative, short in practical terms and large-scale in terms of aesthetics.

The works carried out in cooperation include all young people in the neighborhood, and based on their age and interests, they are directed to useful work.

Paying attention to family, morals and education is one of our duties that is ingrained in our blood. The proverb "One child has seven neighboring parents" is typical of our nation. This proverb itself shows how important it is for us to raise children and family. The people of the neighborhood, especially the elderly, never passed by a child doing a dirty job on the street, and immediately reprimanded him and called him to the right path. After all, our holy religion, which commands to be beautiful, polite, and well-behaved in every way, and to purify the soul, gives great importance to the family. In the process of education, the family and the neighborhood are important, and the interaction of the family and the neighborhood has a great role. In this process, family and neighborhood cooperation, mutual assistance and protection of neighbors are of great importance.

In the process of family upbringing, private relationships, love, respect and description are important. The neighborhood plays an important role in helping the family, helping them find solutions to their problems, and maintaining family relationships. Neighborhood and family partnerships are also important in ensuring the interaction and cooperation of all students. All people in the neighborhood should learn their contribution in the process of developing mutual relations, responding to the interests of young people and raising a family.

Family and neighborhood partnerships are also important in guiding young people on the right path. Neighborhood teachers and family members should help young people develop relationships, learn and master themselves. In addition, family and neighborhood cooperation, discussion and support are of great importance. People in the neighborhood should help the family in solving mutual problems and helping each other. Such situations affect young people in the process of family education and help them to grow into good people. The role of school in child education is also very important. When every child steps on the threshold of school, he imagines what he will do in the future. The knowledge and education acquired at school will definitely have an impact on the implementation of these tasks.

The efficiency will be higher if the following principles are applied in the cooperation of the family, neighborhood, and school:

➤ unity of cooperation in the educational process

➤ harmony of respect and demand for the student.

➤ equal rights and high responsibility of the subjects of the cooperation process. ➤ to ensure the physical, mental and spiritual development of parents and children in the pre-school period.

In conclusion, we would like to inform you that in raising the young generation to be well-behaved and loyal to the motherland, it is necessary to pay attention to their youthful aspects and character. Because without these, the goal of education cannot be achieved. The positive aspects of the neighborhood, school, and family cooperation are that it helps the child to gain worldly knowledge, to have a broad range of ideas, not to give in to wrong influences, to ensure productive spending of free time at home and at school, and to grow up as a person who benefits his people and society.

In conclusion, it can be said that parents and family environment are very important for raising a generation with strong moral immunity, who can express their thoughts fluently, and who can achieve high goals. It is not a secret to anyone, today, when various dangers aimed at poisoning the spiritual world of the youth are intensifying, only the young generation, who deeply understands who they are and what kind of heirs they are, and who lives with love and loyalty to the motherland, and who has strong faith, will be able to protect our holy land from foreign and foreign influences, calamities, and bring prosperity to our Motherland in every way.

Let's educate our children in such a way that they grow up loyal to their ancestors, their history, Motherland, mother tongue, nationality, religion and traditions.

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